

A NOTE ON PARACHOR AND MOLECULAR REFRACTIVITY

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Herz (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 169, 316) from the data available for some 51 organic liquids has shown that the quotient of parachor divided by molecular refractivity is a constant, independent of the nature of the liquid. Preliminary investigation showed that the differences in the values of the constant for different compounds were not negligible. The ratio $[P]/[R]$ for different homologous series of the aliphatic compounds of the type RX (where R is an n -alkyl group and $X = Cl, Br, I, H, OH, SH,$ or NH_2) has been investigated in detail in the present paper (for the values of $[P]$ and $[R]$ vide Vogel *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 171; 1943, 16, 636; 1948, 616, 624, 1814, 1825; Mumford and Phillips, *ibid.*, 1950, 75). The calculated values ($[P]/[R]_{exp}$) are presented in Table I. The results indicate that (i) the ratio has a constant value of 8.60 for n -alkyl bromides; (ii) the ratio has a constant value of 8.50 for n -alkyl mercaptans; (iii) the value of the ratio is decreasing as the series is ascended in the case of n -alkyl chlorides, alcohols and amines and n -paraffins; and (iv) the value of the ratio is increasing as the series is ascended in the case of n -alkyl iodides. It is noted that in the case of those series where the varying values of the ratio are obtained, the values tend to approach a constant value of 8.6 as the series is ascended. Sulphur compounds differ from the rest of the compounds considered here in having a different constant value of 8.50.

TABLE I

(a) n -Alkyl chlorides.				(d) n -Alkyl mercaptans			
n -Alkyl group.	$[P]/[R]_{exp}$.	$[P]/[R]_{der}$.	Diff.	n -Alkyl group.	$[P]/[R]_{exp}$.	$[P]/[R]_{der}$.	Diff.
n -Butyl	9.06	9.03	-0.03	Ethyl	8.51	8.50	+0.01
n -Hexyl	8.94	8.94	± 0.00	n -Butyl	8.53	8.50	+0.03
n -Octyl	8.88	8.87	+0.01	n -Hexyl	8.54	8.50	+0.04
n -Decyl	8.84	8.82	+0.02	n -Octyl	8.51	8.50	+0.01
(b) n -Alkyl bromides.				(e) n -Alkyl alcohols.			
Ethyl	8.69	8.60	+0.09	Ethyl	9.83	9.81	+0.02
n -Butyl	8.67	8.60	± 0.00	n -Butyl	9.27	9.29	-0.02
n -Hexyl	8.60	8.60	± 0.00	n -Hexyl	9.10	9.08	+0.02
n -Octyl	8.61	8.60	+0.01				
n -Decyl	8.60	8.60	± 0.00	(f) n -Alkyl amines.			
				n -Butyl	9.12	9.12	± 0.00
				n -Hexyl	8.97	8.95	+0.01
				n -Octyl	8.84	8.88	-0.04
(c) n -Alkyl iodides.				(g) n -Paraffins.			
Ethyl	7.71	7.68	+0.03	n -Hexane	9.05	9.08	-0.03
n -Butyl	7.99	7.94	-0.04	n -Octane	8.96	8.96	-0.01
n -Hexyl	8.09	8.09	± 0.00	n -Decane	8.86	8.88	-0.02
n -Octyl	8.17	8.18	-0.01				

N.B. Only one half of the compounds investigated are presented in the table.

The values of the ratio for compounds other than sulphur compounds can be calculated from the equation :

$$[P]/[R] = 8.6 \frac{[\sum nuZ + \sum a]}{[\sum nu(A - Z)]}$$

where n is the number of atoms of the elements (other than hydrogen) whose atomic weight, atomic number and valency are A , Z , and v respectively and a is a constant for each element (other than hydrogen). The values of " a " for the elements are :

$$C = +8; N = -1; O = +1; S = 0; I = 0; Br = +2.$$

The values of the ratio for n -alkyl mercaptans can be calculated from the following relation :

$$[P]/[R] = 8.5 \frac{[\sum nuZ]}{[\sum nu(A - Z)]}$$

The values calculated using the above relations are presented in Table I ($[P]/[R]_{\text{calc}}$). The results indicate the close agreement between the experimentally observed and the empirically calculated values.

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Received November 7, 1955.